

Exploring Idioms in the Movie Script of “Moana” by Ron Clements and John Musker

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ABSTRACT

An idiom is a word or phrase whose meaning is not always evident from its literal definition but is implicitly understood by native speakers of a particular culture. This study aims to investigate English Idioms in the movie script “Moana” By Ron Clements and John Musker using a large corpus. Examining usage statistics can provide a general understanding of English idiomatic terms. This study seeks to provide a description of idioms that takes into account Fernando and Heasley’s theory. Based on the research, it can be seen that there are 16 idioms in total from the movie Moana. Fernando’s theory separates these into seven pure, six half-pure, and three literal idioms. On the other hand, Heasley’s theory helps to undergo each of the meanings.

1. Introduction

Communication is one of the most fundamental parts of human interaction, and language is vital to that. It is the responsibility of the speaker to offer context when conveying information. Some believe that a single, pithy sentence is the most effective way to express their message’s essence. Due to the fact that it is easier to say “I am giving up” than “I don’t want to do it anymore,” many individuals do so. It is true that dictionaries sometimes omit entries for common English words. Additionally, there are a few claims and sentences that cannot be articulated formally by the use of grammar. An idiom is a figure of speech used frequently in the English language to emphasize a particular characteristic. Idioms are figurative or slang expressions that cannot be translated literally into another language. In other words, their meanings are more complex than the sum of their individual components. McCarthy and O’Dell (2003: 6) define idioms as fixed phrasal combinations having meanings that cannot be deduced from the meanings of the sentences that comprise the idiom.

The meanings of idioms cannot be discovered through a word-by-word examination of their constituent parts. To comprehend the importance of the concepts under discussion, it is necessary to look beyond the literal meanings of these terms and study the contexts in which they are applied. It is vital to consider the greater context of an idiomatic remark or expression. Failure to do so may result in miscommunication between the speaker and the listener. Due to their importance in the sphere of communication, idioms will be the subject of this research. Understanding proper idioms are essential for effective and transparent communication (Rakhmatullayevna, 2022). Idiom illiteracy makes it difficult to comprehend what others are saying, which can result in misunderstanding and poor communication. When someone says "pull me up," for instance, we cannot take this phrase at its value. To remove a flower from its stem is to pick it; up is the opposite of down. If we take each assertion at face value, we cannot pick someone like a flower since it makes no sense.

Idioms are not explicitly taught in school or university curricula, which is unfortunate given the importance of idiom comprehension for students. Because they will be needed to speak with others in the future, it is vital that pupils obtain a deeper understanding of the subject. Some students have trouble communicating successfully in English because they lack an extensive understanding of idioms. The most efficient way to learn idioms is through listening to actual conversations and seeing how people interact in natural contexts (Grant, 2006).

One of the places where idioms are commonly encountered is in films and movies. Native English speakers typically use idioms, phrasal verbs, and conditional sentences when conversing in English films. Idioms are word combinations whose meaning transcends that of their individual meanings. In one context, it can have a literal meaning, while in another, it can have an idiomatic connotation. It is a term that does not always adhere to traditional meaning and grammar rules. There are numerous idioms in the English language. Idioms may have a different meaning than their literal word counterparts. It is difficult for someone who is not fluent in the language to use them effectively. Idioms are extremely important when learning English because they are frequently used in everyday speech and writing. Idioms would allow English speakers to appear to be native speakers. Idioms are a tried-and-true method of communication; they can be found in every language, and, according to Bakara (2021), they can effectively convey complex ideas with a limited vocabulary. Consequently, they play a crucial part in the many forms of communication. Idioms constitute a challenge not only to language instructors but also to students, but neither group has the luxury of ignoring them.

The best approach to expanding one's vocabulary and learning new idioms is to watch movies. The vast majority of individuals would prefer to learn in an interesting manner, such as by watching a movie. They are able to acquire idiomatic terms and other linguistic nuances through exposure to films in that language. Students may benefit from knowing the meaning of the idioms used throughout the video in order to comprehend the presentation's topic. Despite this, mastering idioms is just one of many challenging aspects of the English language to master. Understanding idioms is difficult for the great majority of people. This particular idiom presents a translation issue since, according to the definition of an idiom, it is a sentence in which the terms together have a meaning that differs from their individual dictionary definitions.

1. Literature Review

2.1 Definitions of Idioms

Previously, there are many types of research that have been done in regard to the use of Idioms, such as Noni Rehulina (2021), which found that Cinema is one of the literary works whose purpose is to both entertain and educate. In the film, the writer concentrates on idiomatic terms since they are utilized in regular English discourse, are a natural part of the language, and are employed not only on special occasions but on every occasion. The author herself chose the film based on its appropriateness for all audiences, especially children. In addition, there are numerous idiomatic idioms in the film. Thus, the movie's idiomatic terms must be translated accurately so as not to cause confusion. Thus, this research would focus not only in terms of children's types of movies. Moana's movie itself is categorized for all ages, and its audience spans several generations. Furthermore, after noticing the widespread use of idioms in movies, the writers were prompted to explore the idiomatic language used in the film "Moana," which was directed by Ron Clements and John Musker.

Subkhan's (2018) "An Analysis of Idiomatic Expressions in the Film American Sniper" is also cited as a source in this investigation. The similarities between this study and his are the focus of the investigation, with the researcher discussing idiomatic expression. The remaining similarities pertain to the type of idiom present in a film. In contrast, this study identifies three categories of idiomatic expression meanings based on Fernando's theory, whereas his study identifies seven types of idiomatic expression meanings found in the film.

Idioms are difficult for most people to comprehend, so we are just interested in counting how often they were used in this film. Moreover, when people translate movies word-for-word without comprehending the idiomatic usage of terminology, they may ignore the fact that certain terms are idioms. This occurs when movies are translated word for word. Despite the fact that the subtitles have been translated, there are some terms that just do not have literal translations.

2.2 Types of Idioms

According to Fernando (1996), there are three categories of idioms.

1. Pure Idioms. The meaning of a Pure Idiom cannot be deduced from an examination of its component parts, as in the case of a literal translation of the words. The idiomatic saying "Spill, Beans" has nothing to do with beans but means "unintentionally divulge a secret."
2. Half-Pure Idiom, there is at least one literal and one figurative element to this idiom. To "pay the bill" is to "foot the bill," for instance. Due to the combination of a non-literal element (foot) and a literal one (bill), we get a semi-pure idiom.
3. Literal Idioms when compared to the other two categories of idioms, literal idioms have a simpler meaning. Bottom of my heart, for example, means "bottom of my heart" in this literal phrase, making it easier to understand even for those who are not accustomed to idioms. Because of its simplicity and straightforward language, this idiom falls under the category of literal idioms.

All these idioms have a totally different meaning from the actual sentence or words. Heasley's theory breaks down the idiom's meaning. According to Heasley (2007), the meaning of idioms is not completely organized. Even though it is impossible to comprehend their literal composition together with their idiomatic connotations, many phrases have the potential to become idioms. Expressions like "let the cat out of the bag" have multiple

meanings depending on the surrounding content. Taking the cat out of the bag literally means exposing a secret, which is the colloquial connotation.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Object

In the work of Meyer and Northridge, a research object is described as anything that can be disassembled and studied to obtain useful information (Meyer:2007). The 2016 animated film *Moana* served as the source material for this study, and the idioms spoken by characters such as *Moana*, *Mau*, and *Moana's father* were the focus of the examination. This featured a significant number of English idioms. After that, idioms themselves became the principal focus of the academic investigation. Only one film needs analysis. The researcher hypothesizes that a movie has a large number of idioms due to the numerous dialogues that occur over the duration of more than an hour.

3.2 Instruments

Data collection is impossible without the right research tool. Qualitative researchers often use people. Researchers are tools. Qualitative research may use three data-gathering approaches. Interview, observation, and documents. This study used films and researchers as research instruments. This study largely used the movie.

This work incorporates qualitative data. Therefore the researcher is crucial to the writing process. This information does not require calculations, unlike quantitative data, which requires. The researcher's data collection skills affect how realistic the picture looks. For document conclusions, the researcher will analyze the film. Informational documents and images were collected. Individual, institutional, and mass documents exist. Personal documentation includes letters, diaries, etc. Official materials include notebooks and files. Popular culture includes books, films, and other media. This inquiry requires a tool. The film was also studied.

3.3 Data Analysis Procedures

Analysis followed data collection. Analyzing data involves these steps:

1. In the first step, the researcher prepares the data for analysis. For this step, the researcher watched the *Moana* Film.
2. The second step was collecting the idioms and reading all the data. The researcher read all the collected data. The researcher tries to understand the information conveyed.
3. The next step is decrypting the data. In this step, the researcher preferred to analyze by employing the framework established by Fernando to categorize idiom types and that established by Heasley to examine the significance of idioms.
4. Finally, the last step is the interpretation of the data. In this step, interpreting and explaining are needed to analyze the problems in understanding the meaning of idiom expressions found.

4. Findings

4.1. Idioms found in the movie *Moana*

The extent to which language speakers are unfamiliar with popular idioms is directly proportional to the degree to which that language is awkward and ineffective in ordinary situations. Idioms are expressions composed of a string of words with no connection outside of their use in the idiom. Idioms are metaphorical expressions whose meanings cannot be deduced from the literal meaning of the words or their regular order of use. This is because

idioms are drawn from oral tradition. While the use of idioms in the movie is not new, it has existed for centuries. In actuality, the use of idioms improves the viewing experience. Many individuals concurred that idioms are captivating and engaging. Moreover, how it is served influences how individuals catch certain movie quotes. To grasp idioms, however, study and comprehension are necessary.

Thus, in Moana Movie by Ron Clements and John Musker, the idioms could be listed as:

Table 1. Idioms in Moana Movie

No.	Idiom Expressions
1.	To turn one's head back
2.	To make our fish disappear
3.	Make way... make way
4.	Chase away our fish
5.	Motunui is paradise
6.	The water is mischievous
7.	When you place your stone, you will raise this whole island higher
8.	Sometimes our strength lies beneath the surface
9.	Whatever just happened, blame it on pig
10.	Stay out of it or you're sleeping in my armpit
11.	Just pick an eye, babe
12.	Listen to your heart
13.	I will sparkle like a wealthy woman's neck
14.	A diamond in the rough
15.	But your armour's just not hard enough
16.	Because you are a chicken

5. Discussion

Fernando asserts that the maximum limit contains no more than two subordinate clauses. Fernando contends that a typical multiword sentence does not need to possess this characteristic to be categorized as an idiom. Rather, idioms demonstrate a spectrum of literalness. Pure idioms are non-literal, such as *spill the beans*; half pure idioms comprise at least one literal constituent sense and at least one non-literal constituent sense, such as *drop names*; and literal idioms have no non-literal component, such as *tall, dark, and handsome*. Thus the three types of idioms could be understood as follows:

1. A pure idiom is a non-literal expression that has a meaning that cannot be understood by translating word to word. Pure idioms usually have a non-literal meaning.
2. A half pure-idiom at least has one literal word and one non-literal word element.
3. A literal meaning is when a word or phrase is used exactly as it is defined

The table shows how the idioms are being separated:

Table 2. Idioms expression based on Fernando's theory

No.	Idiom Expressions	Type of Idioms (Fernando's theory)
1.	<i>To turn one's head back</i>	Pure Idioms
2.	<i>To make our fish disappear</i>	Half Pure Idioms
3.	<i>Make way... make way</i>	Literal Idioms
4.	<i>Chase away our fish</i>	Half Pure Idioms
5.	<i>Motunui is paradise</i>	Literal Idioms
6.	<i>The water is mischievous</i>	Half Pure Idioms
7.	<i>When you place your stone, you will raise this whole island higher</i>	Pure Idioms
8.	<i>Sometimes our strength lies beneath the surface</i>	Half Pure Idioms
9.	<i>Whatever just happened, blame it on pig</i>	Pure Idioms
10.	<i>Stay out of it or you're sleeping in my armpit</i>	Half Pure Idioms
11.	<i>Just pick an eye, babe</i>	Pure Idioms
12.	<i>Listen to your heart</i>	Literal Idioms
13.	<i>I will sparkle like a wealthy woman's neck</i>	Pure Idioms
14.	<i>A diamond in the rough</i>	Pure Idioms
15.	<i>But your armour's just not hard enough</i>	Half Pure Idioms
16.	<i>Because you are a chicken</i>	Pure Idioms

The table shows that the first type of idiom is a pure idiom whose components have no literal relationship to the phrase's meaning. For instance, "to turn one's head back" does not mean that the person's head will be turned, but to return something to the owner. In addition, half pure, or semi--pure, on the other hand, has at least one literal element and one with a non-literal meaning. In Moana, for example, "to make our fish disappear" means that the person wants to drive away unwanted aquatic organisms, but it does not mean to make them

disappear literally. The last type is literal idioms, which means exactly how it is worded, "listen to your heart". For instance, that means believing in your inner feelings.

Fernando's theory is more on separating the idioms into three categories, as shown in the previous table. Meanwhile, Heasley's theory helps in regards to understanding the meanings. Additionally, the author employs Heasley's (2007) theory to break down the idiom's meaning. According to Heasley, the meaning of idioms is not completely organized. Even though it is impossible to comprehend their literal composition together with their idiomatic connotations, many phrases have the potential to become idioms. Expressions like "Just pick an eye" have multiple meanings depending on the surrounding content. Generally, it means to choose something that could count as the best part, which is the colloquial connotation. Colloquial connotation is an informal style of writing that refers to informal speech patterns or usages. Colloquial is frequently used incorrectly with a connotation of disapproval, as if it meant "vulgar" or "bad" or "incorrect" usage. In contrast, it simply refers to an informal speaking and writing manner.

Table 3. Comparison of Idiom expressions based on different theories

Idiom Expressions	Type of Idioms (Fernando's theory)	Meaning (Heasley's theory)
<i>To turn one's head back</i>	Pure Idioms	means to return
<i>To make our fish disappear</i>	Half Pure Idioms	means the act of driving away unwanted aquatic organisms.
<i>Make way... make way</i>	Literal Idioms	means that you should prepare to make room for something
<i>Chase away our fish</i>	Half Pure Idioms	means to drive something because of unfortunate events
<i>Motunui is paradise</i>	Literal Idioms	means to portray the happiness that permeates their native land.
<i>The water is mischievous</i>	Half Pure Idioms	means that the water (noun/ situation) has a lot of surprises in store
<i>When you place your stone, you will raise this whole island higher</i>	Pure Idioms	means to push the person to decide and help the people of their own
<i>Sometimes our strength lies beneath the surface</i>	Half Pure Idioms	means that the key to our success is the fearlessness of our own
<i>Whatever just happened, blame it on pig</i>	Pure Idioms	means that the person who is being blamed is blameless
<i>Stay out of it or you're sleeping in my armpit</i>	Half Pure Idioms	means to keep away from that at all costs, or else she/he will be having an

		extremely unpleasant situation.
<i>Just pick an eye, babe</i>	Pure Idioms	means to select and take the best parts of something for oneself.
<i>Listen to your heart</i>	Literal Idioms	means following your inner feelings if you want to achieve fulfilment

Finally, the table is complete with idioms found, the breakdown of Fernando's theory and meaning based on Heasley's theory from the movie Moana. It could be acknowledged that there are a lot of idioms being employed. The total is 16 idioms. Fernando separated them into three different categories, whereas in this film, there are seven pure idioms and six half-pure idioms, and 3 literal idioms. On the other hand, Heasley's theory helps to undergo each of the meanings. In the end, Idioms are colorful ways to express yourself, but very few people use them because they are not commonly understood.

6. Conclusion

An idiom is a phrase, the meaning of which is determined by the combination of a number of other words. People commonly turn to the use of symbols when they want to communicate a difficult concept in the clearest and most effective way possible. Based on the research, it can be seen that there are 16 idioms in total from the movie Moana. Fernando's theory separates these into seven pure idioms and six half-pure idioms, and three literal idioms. On the other hand, Heasley's theory helps to undergo each of the meanings. In the end, Idioms are colorful ways to express yourself, but very few people use them because they are not commonly understood. Thus, Employing idioms in a movie is a great help to engage with the viewers, as well as a wonderful way to learn English in a fun and entertaining way.

As part of the educational process, teachers are responsible for ensuring that their students have a comprehensive understanding of idiomatic expressions. If a teacher desires that his or her students become more proficient with idiomatic expressions, he or she can provide opportunities for students to practice using them in context. In addition, students can learn to comprehend and correctly interpret idiomatic idioms when the topic is the focus of specific teachings. This is due to the fact that idioms have unique meanings that cannot be translated literally. Because idiomatic expressions are so prevalent in the commonplace speech of native speakers, it is essential that English learners acquire a deeper understanding of them. They can study it independently and also take up idiomatic language. Students can learn idiomatic expressions from a variety of English-language media, such as novels, songs, films, and television programs.

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